

User Emotional Correlates of Emojis to Derivatives Using Intelligent Analytics

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Abstract

An emerging paradigm in the age of big data is the development of intelligent analytics, which is a branch of Analytics and Artificial Intelligence (AI). This paper explores the nature of intelligent analytics more specifically by identifying the foundations and applications to areas like Affective computing by integrating emotional emojis to users' emotional responses to how they can solve and understand the steps to the solution to ordinary differential equations. The method is derived from investigations into state-of-the-art scholars and research into applications of e-learning and marketing analysis of advanced analytics. Some of the work presents a novel approach to extend intelligent data analytics to intelligent analytics that facilitates research and development of intelligent analytics for AI and Data Science, but none has critically investigated on application of intelligent analytics in affective computing and human-computer interaction (HCI). The paper presents a novel method of modeling user emotional response to the complex differential equation by presenting a synchronous data sequence to the dynamic control model that maps user emotion or affect state to how they solve problems to differential equations. The proposed model is robust and can also present the system performance in predicting the user response that would lead to the decision of how to simplify problem-solving in mathematical calculus.

Keywords : Intelligent Analytics, Emotional emoji, Affective computing, E-learning User emotional response, Dynamic system,

1 Introduction

In recent times, emoji have played a very fundamental role in human-computer interaction and communications by allowing the latter to convey body language, symbols, and ideas in text messages with object identification by using a form of Unicode standardisation pictographs and logographs.

The emojis allow people to express more authentic emotions and their personalities, by increasing the semantic content of the visual messages they narrate. The relationship between this language, emoji, and emotion is now being studied extensively through intelligent analytics that makes a proper presentation of affect state to visual contents with subjective methods.

These methods are most studied in psychology, natural language processing, and machine learning.

The concept behind them is employed for the automatic detection of emotions and personality traits, by building emoji sentiment lexicons as well as conveying the artificial agents with the ability to express emotions through emoji. In this paper, we present a customised method of detecting how users solve an ordinary differential equation and predict their mood by linking it to every step in the solution of the given problem. Most students find it hard to deal with assignment problems in an online or visible lecture on mathematical problems and the problem can help interpret and predict user emotion through emojis that would lead to simple and explicit steps in the solution of the differential equations. Some of the concepts in the use of emojis have shown that the main challenge of using this as a proxy way of communicating users' emotions is productive in assisting e-learning classes. Machine learning and natural language processing techniques use classification and detection of emotions using emojis by presenting new trends for the exploitation of discovered emotional patterns for objects like robotic emotional communication.

2 Literature Review

Basic big data analytics is usually a systematic computational analysis of data on a regular statistical problem and is not usually related to physical problems, but current times refer to ways of dealing with user behavioural data and its attributes by integrating intelligent analytics that would help generate system sequence of data and interpret it in the most basic and simplified terms [16, 10]. Analytics is used for the discovery, communication, interpretation, and conveying of meaningful patterns in user behaviour data. It also entails the application of data patterns toward effective decision-making. Its procedures are valuable in areas that are rich with the recording of information, analytics relies on the synchronous application of computational models and predictive tools to quantify and qualify performance rates. Most organisations and E-learning sites apply analytics to data to describe and predict performance [30, 31, 3, 34, 22, 15, 32, 14, 27, 8, 28]. The areas within analytics include descriptive analytics, prescriptive analytics, diagnostic analytics, predictive analytics, and cognitive analytics for an online system. The algorithms and software used for analytics harness the most current methods in both mathematical and computing science. To understand the concept and how to develop analytics for behaviour studies, people analytics needs to be a major step in the process.

2.1 People Analytics

People analytics uses generated behavioural data to understand how the user works and change how to manage certain ways of simplifying processing speed. People analytics known as workforce analytics in human resource analytics is based on talent, people insight, and people's cognitive state of how they perceive certain products. Data from online resources are usually unstructured and contain user behavioural events such as mouse click, key-press, and fixation location that includes being integrated into physiological response [7, 11, 21, 4, 29, 24, 17, 23, 20, 6, 25, 1]. This unstructured data is a challenge in getting attention in the development of modification strategies. Unstructured data differs from structured data in the sense that its format is different in wider ways and cannot be stored traditionally on a relational database without a significant effect on data filter and anomaly detection [26, 12, 9, 2]. Multimodal intelligent analytics can be developed to manage varieties of complexity in this form of data and the model presented is the engine to handle multi-tasking analytics to the behavioural data derived for identifying a way to simplify problem-solving in online systems in massively parallel processing by the distributed workload in a single system with access to the external integrated tools that generate data [26, 12, 9, 2, 13, 33, 19, 5, 18].

3 Method

The initial stage of the process is to design a framework that involves defining users' perceptions of an online problem-solving system that has a differential equation as its module. The student's cognitive limit is first tested by giving them simple problems to solve based on cognitive assessment using emoticons (Figure 1). The correlates to emotional expression are assigned a critical point that leads to a more stepwise method of solving the same differential equation but with each explicit step. This leads to user self-approval and initiates a salient mental cognition that induces and increases the level of comprehension. The emotion, mood, and affective state are similar but distinct and one of them can be used to classify the perception of the users. The state space then tells us the resulting mood of the user and a conclusive mental description of the user's mood and satisfaction with the solved problem.

3.1 Task

An experimental study was set up, where students were simply asked to solve certain differential equation problems given to them in an online study session. They were asked to solve the differential equations with different procedures. The aim is to monitor their cognitive state and identify certain points in the solution steps

FIGURE 1 – Framework for design of a User’s emotional response to differential equation conveyed by emojis.

that cause stress in perception. The analytic is also initially designed to monitor the stress response based on fixation location, fixation duration, and pupil response. The pupillary response is simply based on dilation and constriction which are classified as stress, relaxed, and neutral if it is detected as lying between stress and relaxed mood. Though pupil dilation is not yet an authentic way of conveying a user’s emotional response, some studies have shown it is very realistic when measuring the cognitive level of a person and has to be processed with great accuracy. The users were asked to interact with the mathematical problem while their eye movements were recorded. A stress emoji will appear when a student experiences some form of difficulty while trying to understand the steps in the solutions to the differential equation. The cognitive state initiates a stress emoji that automatically results in a display of the explicit solution to the problem this minimises stress response.

4 Result

Figure 2 shows a window interface with the emotional response of the user to the different stages of problem-solving. The given problem has two ways of solving it and each assigned step has a solution to the problem, a relaxed emoji would appear if the user finds the solution to the problem easy to understand while the stress emoji simply automates the process to a high level with explicit steps to the solution (Figure 3). Students usually find it difficult to solve the algorithm of an ordinary differential equation, using the initial value problem with the integrating factor method.

The basic steps here illustrate the product rule as an

easy way of teaching the student to solve the differential equation of any order. Many students have difficulty with the material factor of an integral part of calculus, hence the experimental study is aimed at analysing student error in terms of mathematical proof and simple procedures to arrive at the solution, and the detected cognitive response is used to optimise their level of cognition and understanding. One of the aims is also to analyse the difficulties faced by students in the algorithm. Figure 3 shows a window interface that displays descriptive steps in the algorithm proof to the given problem.

One of the characteristics of intelligent analytics is its ability to compute and produce system information about the pattern recognition of each of the attributes of the user behavioural data. The system performance is capable of system report generation and resultant module specification. Figure 3 shows the system report of the control motor dynamics. The performance rate is measured based on an exponential function which can range from $-0.02e^5 - 0.02e^5$. The performance for pupil change shows an error rate of (0.45%) which is feasible for behaviour data and more probable regarding the complexity of the problem. However, the dynamic control system is a standard method and is already trained to possess error rejection capabilities which would increase the performance rate. Hence for the three classes of emotions, the predictions are accurate and could be feasible for modification in the future method of approach.

The product rule in the window interface of Figure3, shows the simplest method of solving the product rule that allows for the calculation of the derivatives that can’t be multiplied in the shortest means of time. The method allows for the determining of the derivative of the two differentiable functions that are being multiplied

FIGURE 2 – Window interface with solution steps to the differential equation and detected user emotional response as mapped emoji to the stress coordinates.

together by combining the power rule and sum of the difference rule, this simplifies the expression, by taking the derivative of each part. The next step is applying the constant rule and constant multiple power rule. The emotional emoji simply automates the response to each narrative to the next window, that is the explicit steps to the main solution. The stress mood detected has a significant influence on task performance. If the impact of the stress goes up beyond the level of tolerance, then it is referred to as a negative effect in terms of error solution, and the cognitive level is then low at that rate. The integrated window allows for stress reduction and an increase in cognitive level by simplification of the solution steps.

The control motor dynamics uses a time-identified state space model, with order three due to reaction to basic stimuli, for the case, the stimuli induce a significant reaction to the complex differential problem and the rate of change of reaction as a result of sweat-cursed by the intense concentration, the rate of change of reaction can be simulated based on order three; i.e. the maximum rate of change in reaction to stress is simulated with this phasic change and equals the stress state of a person. A relaxed mood is induced when the rate of moisture content is at its minimal rate and induces a calm ambiance. The physiological response (SCR, ST, and Pupil change) is quantified based on the response measure and also correlates to fixation location and fixation duration. Figure 4 shows the parameters with the most contribution to the model performance and response detection,

SCR and ST have an error rate of 0.04% and 0.08%, this is less than the estimated rate of 0.1% and feasible for response detection in a complex data sequence from behaviour response statistics.

5 Conclusion

This paper investigates intelligent analytics in user emotional correlates of emojis on solutions to differential equations, some studies usually focus on a workflow-based approach to big data analytics and the technological foundations for intelligent data analytics by examining intelligent data generated from online and local sources. Some of the work presents a novel approach to extend intelligent data analytics to intelligent analytics that facilitates research and development of intelligent analytics for AI and Data Science, but none has critically investigated on application of intelligent analytics in affective computing and human-computer interaction (HCI). The paper presents a novel method of modelling user emotional response to complex differential equations by presenting a synchronous data sequence to the dynamic control model that maps user emotion or affects state to how they solve problems to differential equations. The proposed model is robust and can also present the system performance in predicting the user response that would lead to the decision of how to simplify problem-solving in mathematical calculus. The design phase would involve the integration of a complex but simplified method of analytics integrated with effective model performance

FIGURE 3 – An automatic interface induced by the stress response to the explicit steps to a mathematical problem.

FIGURE 4 – User parameter estimate in terms of best attributes that contributes most to model performance.

and optimisation.

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